

Bathymetry-aided Underwater Acoustic Localization using a Single Passive Receiver^a

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1 This paper considers the problem of estimating the trajectory of an autonomous underwater
2 vehicle (AUV) via a single passive receiver, without any anchor nodes or receiving arrays,
3 and with the only help of a sequence of known acoustic signals emitted by the AUV. This
4 scenario is of interest in case multilateration-based alternatives would require the deploy-
5 ment of many receivers and imply exceedingly high costs, e.g., for the coverage of wide
6 areas. The proposed method exploits the knowledge of environmental parameters such as
7 the sound speed profile, bathymetry and bottom sediments in order to estimate the loca-
8 tion of the AUV, taking advantage of the spatial dependency of channel impulse responses
9 that arises from the diverse bathymetry around the receiver. This dependency is captured
10 by comparing channel estimates against a database of channel responses, pre-computed
11 through an acoustic propagation model. This yields multiple likely AUV locations, which
12 are filtered via a path tracking method similar to the Viterbi algorithm, in order to estimate
13 the trajectory of the AUV. Results obtained both from simulations and from a sea experi-
14 ment show that the proposed method can estimate node locations and paths with a small
15 error, especially considering the use of a single receiver.

^aA preliminary version of this work has been presented at the IEEE WPNC 2017 conference, Bremen, Germany¹.

16 I. INTRODUCTION

17 Estimating the location of an autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) is a required step for the
18 operation of these devices for applications like ocean exploration, control of secure areas, and en-
19 vironmental monitoring. In these applications, the AUV covers large areas, and its self-navigation
20 system may drift significantly. Localizing the AUV via non-inertial systems may greatly help
21 reduce such drift and improve the AUV's location reckoning. Localization is typically achieved
22 through a set of fixed receiving hydrophones spread across the AUV deployment area. Yet, due to
23 the wide area covered by the AUV during its mission, its transmissions tend to be detected very
24 sparsely over both space and time. This is especially the case if the AUV's mission area is very
25 large, and would imply the (expensive) deployment of a significant amount of equipment in order
26 to cover the intended area with a sufficient density to enable reliable multilateration estimates.
27 Instead, in order to balance a reasonable target detection probability with long term deployment
28 constraints and costs, the coverage of large areas is typically achieved through sparse deployments.
29 As a result, it is often the case that the signals used to detect a target are practically received only
30 by a single receiver. Most existing algorithms to localize submerged devices require the presence
31 of several anchor nodes², or prescribe message exchanges between the device and the anchors³.
32 Alternatively, range estimates from a single mobile anchor have been suggested assuming knowl-
33 edge of the receiver's movement between subsequent transmissions through, e.g., acceleration
34 measurements⁴. Yet, this also requires interaction with the device to be localized.

35 In this paper, we offer a solution for the challenge of localizing a non-collaborative single
36 AUV. As opposed to localization methods that rely on a receiving array, our method assumes
37 only the presence of a single stationary and passive receiving element, and the knowledge of the

38 transmitted signal (for example, the structure of the AUV pinger’s signals), but does not require
39 knowledge of the pinger’s transmission times. Our approach is inspired by localization algorithms
40 based on fingerprinting⁵: these algorithms evaluate the correlation between some significant and
41 distinguishable channel characteristics (e.g., the power-delay profile, the number of distinguish-
42 able arrivals, the angular spectrum of these arrivals, and so forth), and the same characteristics
43 preliminarily measured at a number of locations, and collected together in a fingerprint database.
44 Instead, our method hinges on the spatial diversity of the sea bottom bathymetry to match the
45 measured channel impulse response (CIR) with a set of CIRs generated through an acoustic prop-
46 agation model. To that end, we target those environments where the bathymetry and the sound
47 speed profile (SSP) in the water column induce different channel impulse responses for different
48 emitter-receiver location pairs. This is often the case for shallow-water environments with a di-
49 verse non-flat bathymetry, but also for deeper waters where sea bottom hills, mountains, or steep
50 slopes may exist.

51 We base our method on the modeling of expected acoustic CIRs for different possible locations
52 of an acoustic source around the moored receiver. After measuring the CIR for each received
53 signal, we correlate it with the pre-computed modeled CIRs in order to estimate the distance,
54 depth and bearing of the transmitter. This makes it possible to point the location of the sound-
55 emitting AUV to the position for which the modeled CIR best fits the measured CIR. We repeat
56 the process as the AUV moves and keeps emitting signals. The result is a sequence of location
57 estimates whose size equals the number of detected sound emissions. These location estimates
58 are expected to be noisy, since there may be several modeled CIRs that are significantly correlated
59 with each measured CIR. To filter this noise, we create a trellis of possible locations, which are

60 chosen from the output of the cross-correlation between the modeled and measured CIRs, and
61 which satisfy a given maximum AUV speed. The final path of the AUV is obtained via an efficient
62 trellis search process similar to the Viterbi algorithm.

63 Our contribution is twofold:

- 64 • A localization approach for an AUV using a single receiving element;
- 65 • An efficient method to reduce the state space resulting from the cross-correlation of modeled
66 and measured CIRs, and thereby significantly decrease the complexity of the AUV path
67 estimation process.

68 We evaluate our method through both simulations (based on real bathymetry and sound speed
69 information) and a proof-of-concept sea trial. Our results show that the proposed approach can
70 estimate the AUV path with an acceptable localization error.

71 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides an account of related
72 work; Section III details the localization algorithm; Section IV presents simulation results; Sec-
73 tion V describes our proof-of-concept sea trial; Section VI concludes the paper.

74 II. RELATED WORK

75 A. Techniques for Underwater Acoustic Localization

76 A comprehensive survey of underwater acoustic localization is presented in^{6,7}, and involves
77 techniques for range estimation, bearing estimation, or both. Typical approaches to localization
78 include long baseline (LBL)⁷ (based on trilateration, and thus requiring the interaction between
79 the device to be localized and the anchors), short baseline (SBL, usually operated from a single
80 vessel) and ultra-short baseline (USBL) systems⁸, that estimate the location of the device via time

81 of arrival (ToA) and angle of arrival (AoA) measurements. As the accuracy of the angle estimation
82 process directly depends on the stability of the equipment and is sensitive to strong multipath,
83 range-based approaches are more typically used.

84 Typical underwater ranging schemes rely on ToA, time difference of arrival (TDoA), or re-
85 ceived signal strength (RSS), which is translated into distance via an acoustic propagation model⁹.
86 ToA measurements can be obtained by separately analyzing the reflection patterns of transmitted
87 signals¹⁰, which can be estimated via matched filtering or by using phase-only correlation and
88 the kurtosis metric to mitigate channel-enhanced noise¹¹. Still, ToA measurements tend to be
89 noisy due to multipath: mistaking a non-specular multipath component for the direct path is often
90 regarded as measurement noise¹², and can be mitigated by transmitting signals having a narrow
91 auto-correlation^{13,14}, or by averaging ToA measurements over different signals¹⁵. Yet, instead of
92 considering multipath as a distortion, the wealth of multipath arrivals can be exploited in passive
93 systems in order to improve the localization accuracy, as well as to find the range of the acoustic
94 source¹⁶ or to localize it with multiple receivers through a propagation model¹⁷.

95 In the literature, the closest approaches to our proposed scheme target localization with less
96 than three reference nodes, often by exploiting some form of knowledge about the environment.
97 For example, the work in¹⁸ introduced a model-based range-bearing localization scheme that em-
98 ploys two receiving hydrophones. The method identifies multipath arrivals at the hydrophones
99 and tracks them using a particle filter. An ambiguity surface is then constructed based on the ex-
100 pected multipath structure (derived via a ray model) and used to determine the most likely target
101 location. To localize a source, the work in⁵ proposes to match received signals against a set of
102 fingerprints measured by an array of receivers. The authors test the feasibility their approach in a

103 pool, which represents a static environment where fingerprints remain sufficiently stable over time.
104 However, systematic fingerprint measurements in uncontrolled open sea environments would be
105 more challenging, due to the rapidly changing nature of underwater acoustic channels.

106 Matched-field processing, a family of array processing-based methods to estimate the param-
107 eters of the ocean waveguide based on the full field structure of acoustic signals, can also be
108 extended to underwater localization¹⁹. For example, the work in²⁰ assumes the three-dimensional
109 knowledge of the SSP and of the bathymetry over a 600×600 km² area. The area is further divided
110 in squares of side 5 km and normal mode theory is employed to predict sound propagation for a
111 hypothetical source located in the center of each square. The sound field replicas thus obtained
112 are matched to the acoustic field measurements collected through a 21-element vertical array, in
113 order to infer the most likely location of the source. Matched-field localization has been recently
114 achieved using compressed sensing (CS), which has the advantage of providing sparse solutions to
115 inference problems using convex optimization²¹. Specifically, the proposed approach employs CS
116 (implemented through the basis pursuit algorithm and the Lasso path) to find the best matching
117 between field replicas and measurements, and shows that CS reliably handles coherent sources
118 as well. Earlier, CS was considered to localize an underwater device by means of ultrawideband
119 radio CIR fingerprinting²². Here, CS is implemented using the orthogonal matching pursuit and
120 Lasso-II algorithms. Although the method achieves good localization accuracy, it remains suit-
121 able only for very short ranges, due to the strong attenuation of RF waves in salted waters. An
122 approach to estimate the range of a source with respect to a single receiver is presented in²³. The
123 authors assume that a moving source transmits signals with a period Δt while moving around a
124 hydrophone, and determine striation patterns in the function relating the signal observation time to

125 Δt . These these patterns are then employed to infer the velocity and range of the source, based on
126 the assumption that the ranging operations take place in a shallow-water environment with wave-
127 uide invariant $\beta = 1$. When β is unknown, the Automatic Identification System (AIS) of nearby
128 vessels can be opportunistically used to estimate it, by relating their received signal, intensity and
129 frequency to their known position²⁴.

130 The presence of an array of transmitters is assumed in²⁵, where the authors pre-compute the
131 CIR from each transmitter to at all points of a grid that finely covers the water column along a
132 given bearing. The location of a receiver is estimated by comparing the CIRs measured by the
133 receiver against pre-computed CIRs. The system finally employs the determined location to tune
134 transmit beamforming. In²⁶, an AUV is located by fusing AUV heading and velocity information
135 from some external sensor with acoustic phase information. The phase is measured from a batch
136 of signals transmitted by a fixed projector of known location and received by a single hydrophone
137 at the AUV.

138 **B. Differences with respect to Indoor Localization**

139 While fingerprinting is an established localization technique for terrestrial radio networks^{27,28},
140 one of its key assumptions is that radio measurements are repeatable and slowly varying in space²⁹,
141 so that a device can actually afford to compute several statistics of a received radio signal and fuse
142 them into a fingerprint vector³⁰. Conversely, the underwater acoustic channel tends to be much
143 more dynamic, with several arrivals coming from multiple reflection over the surface, bottom and
144 volume scatterers. Moreover, the spatial coherence of the underwater channel is very limited, and a
145 transmitter could experience very different channels when communicating to a static receiver from

146 different locations. Similar uses of ray tracing to aid indoor localization (e.g., see³¹) typically do
147 not experience these issue, as they can rely on more stable radio channels. Filtering multiple
148 sequential measurements through the Viterbi algorithm³² or other techniques (such as probabil-
149 ity maps reproducing the expected movement of mobile devices³³ or conditional random fields³⁴)
150 makes it possible to eliminate this uncertainty. However, the number of possible indoor positions
151 to be matched by a terrestrial radio fingerprinting algorithm is usually very limited, yielding a
152 state space of tractable size. On the contrary, in our underwater approach the location of the target
153 could be anywhere around the location of the single receiver, yielding an order-of- 10^7 state space
154 size. This calls for methods to reduce the complexity of trellis exploration. We also remark that
155 direction-of-arrival fingerprinting-based localization has been reconsidered in the field of millime-
156 ter wave communications (e.g., see^{35,36}), where however the devices can leverage large arrays to
157 reliably decouple propagation paths in the received angular spectra. This is in contrast with our
158 assumption of using a single receiving element, and remains very different from the rich CIRs
159 usually measured in underwater communications.

160 C. Summary

161 The literature that most closely relates to our paper is summarized in Table I, where we report
162 the requirements, description, and shortcomings of each approach. From this comparison, it be-
163 comes clear that the most prominent contribution of our approach is the localization of a moving
164 AUV in 3D using a single receiver (and assuming only a single transmitter at the AUV). While our
165 approach has some aspects in common with matched field processing and fingerprinting, it remains
166 unique in that it reduces the ambiguity of the matching between measured and pre-computed CIRs

TABLE I. Summary of the most relevant related work

Ref.	Approach	Requirements	Details	Shortcomings
18 (2015)	Multipath tracking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two receivers • Known environmental parameters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compare multipath vs. ray model • Particle filter extracts arrivals • Ambiguity surface search 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assumes isovelocity profile
5 (2009)	Finger-printing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fingerprint database • Broadband signal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database of modeled CIRs • Pattern matching of CIR measurements at different frequencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple receivers • Maintenance of fingerprint database in ocean environments
20 (1990)	Matched field processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydrophone array • Known environmental parameters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acoustic field replica computation • Gridded virtual source positioning • ML or Bartlett processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires multiple receivers to decrease ambiguity
22 (2014)	Radio UWB finger-printing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UWB radio modeling to pre-compute field dictionary • Multiple antennas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UWB fingerprinting • CS solution via orthogonal matching pursuit and Lasso-II 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple antennas • Limited to short-range localization
21 (2017)	Compressed sensing for matched field processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydrophone array • Known environmental parameters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acoustic field replica computation • CS solution via basis pursuit and Lasso 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple receivers
23 (2012)	Range estimation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single receiver • Known waveguide invariant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source velocity computation • Identification of point closest to receiver 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Range-only
25 (2018)	Finger-printing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Known environmental parameters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIR computation over a fine 2D vertical grid • Matching with measurements from multiple transmitters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple projectors • Fixed-bearing localization
26 (2014)	Acoustics-aided inertial tracking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External bearing/speed sensor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract phase from train of sine waves • Solves inverse problem to determine AUV location 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires accurate bearing/speed measurements

FIG. 1. Block diagram of the AUV location and path estimation algorithm.

167 through a trellis search approach similar to the Viterbi algorithm, rather than resorting to fusing
 168 information from multiple transmitters or receivers. Moreover, we only process acoustic data, and
 169 do not require any external sensors to support the localization process.

170 With respect to the preliminary work in¹, the algorithm presented in this paper is much less
 171 sensitive to trellises that are not fully connected and to imperfect estimates of the initial AUV
 172 location; in addition, we include a performance verification through a sea experiment, and compare
 173 against benchmark approaches both in the simulations and in the sea experiment.

174 III. ALGORITHM DESCRIPTION

175 A. Key Idea

176 We summarize the key idea behind our algorithm with the help of the flow chart in Fig. 1.
 177 We operate the AUV localization algorithm from a single receiver deployed at a known and well-
 178 explored stationary location. We assume that the sea bottom is diverse around the receiver (e.g.,
 179 see Fig. 2), leading to a spatially-dependent CIR, which we exploit in order to estimate the location
 180 of the AUV via a fingerprinting-based location system. Since such a system requires to measure a
 181 three-dimensional database of fingerprints (which is not feasible in underwater scenarios due to the

(a) Map of the San Diego bay area, showing a variable bathymetry, the location of the receiver and of two transmitters, and the sea bottom profiles between each transmitter and the receiver. (b) Example of SSP measured in the area

(c) CIR from transmitter 1 to the receiver.

(d) CIR from transmitter 2 to the receiver.

FIG. 2. Illustration of our single-receiver localization method. When the environment is sufficiently diverse (a), the CIRs differ significantly across different locations (c), (d). This can be leveraged for localization.

182 resource- and time-intensiveness of underwater acoustic measurements), we resort to a database of
 183 modeled CIRs instead. Such database is pre-computed via a numerical sound propagation model,
 184 such as the Bellhop ray tracing simulator (see Ch. 3 in³⁷ and³⁸).

185 Whenever an acoustic signal is received from the AUV, we estimate the CIR of the correspond-
 186 ing acoustic channel and correlate it with our database. In order to reduce the complexity of this

187 step, we first correlate the CIR with specular and surface-reflected arrivals from the modeled CIRs:
188 this excludes bearing-dependent bottom arrivals, and allows us to retrieve a set of possible values
189 for the AUV’s depth and distance. We then compute one further round of cross-correlations, this
190 time with the whole channel impulse response (thus including bottom reflections), for the selected
191 depths and distances, and for every bearing value. The result is a number of possible AUV loca-
192 tions. We repeat the process for several subsequent acoustic signals emitted from the AUV, which
193 may correspond to the same location, or to different locations in case the AUV is moving. Finally,
194 we apply an efficient, low-complexity tracking mechanism in order to filter all matching locations
195 found, and to obtain a source trajectory estimate.

196 Fig. 3 presents an example of the output of four subsequent location estimates. Each of panels
197 (a) through (d) shows a map of the scenario. Our single receiver is shown as a centrally located
198 square, whereas the AUV that moves along the trajectory represented as a black line. At each
199 of the positions marked by two concentric circles, the AUV emits a signal that is employed by
200 the receiver to compute location estimates as explained above. In panels (a)-(d), these location
201 estimates are represented as grey crosses, where a darker grey shade indicates a higher confidence.
202 The algorithm outputs multiple estimates for each AUV location, each with a different levels of
203 confidence (higher confidence is represented using a darker grey shade in panels (a)–(d). Note that
204 the the point of highest confidence may not be the closest to the actual AUV location.

205 To rule out spurious estimates, we order the computed locations into a trellis (Fig. 3e), and run
206 a forward-backward path search procedure similar to the Viterbi algorithm. In this case, the black
207 path in Fig. 3e is selected, corresponding to the trajectory shown in Fig. 3f.

FIG. 3. High-level illustration of the key idea behind our single-receiver localization process. Panels (a)–(d) show a sound source moving along a straight trajectory. At four locations, the source emits a signal. The receiver (located at the center of the area) measures the CIR and compares it against a database of modeled channel responses. This translates into the location estimates indicated by the crosses, where a darker grey shade indicates higher confidence. A trellis search algorithm (e) is then applied to find the most likely source path (panel (f)).

208 **B. Preliminary Assumptions and Setup**

209 The first step to localize the AUV is to detect is periodic pinger signals. We assume that no prior
 210 information is available about the location, the instantaneous speed, or the trajectory of the AUV,

211 and that the AUV does not collaborate to the localization process. Hence, a solution based on
 212 updating the parameters of a dynamic model for the AUV through filtering is not an option in our
 213 scenario. We only assume that the emitted signal's waveform is either known, or can be reliably
 214 estimated, such that the channel impulse response can be evaluated. By this, we take into account
 215 received multipath, but ignore interference. Hence, our method is geared into the localization
 216 of a single source. We assume that an initial survey has been carried out in order to measure
 217 the bathymetry of the area surrounding the moored receiver with a fine resolution. The 1-meter
 218 resolution obtained by a 400-kHz multibeam sonar (see our experimental results in Section V) is
 219 more than sufficient in this respect. We further require periodic direct or indirect measurements of
 220 the local SSP.

221 The area explored to localize the AUV is limited by the coverage of the bathymetry measure-
 222 ments, by the reception capabilities of the receiver, and by constraints on the emitter's source level.
 223 This yields a bounded depth range between z_{\min}^s and z_{\max}^s . We further assume the AUV is moving
 224 at an absolute maximum speed of v_{\max}^s , known to the receiver. This leads to an expectation on
 225 the maximum distance traveled by the AUV between two subsequent emissions. We note that the
 226 knowledge of the AUV's maximum speed is not strictly required, but the availability of this infor-
 227 mation improves the performance and greatly reduces the complexity of our method. At different
 228 locations, indexed by $n = 1, \dots, N_L$, the source emits acoustic signals that are detected by the
 229 receiver along with each significant multipath arrival. The locations are expressed in terms of a
 230 cylindrical coordinate system as $\mathbf{x}_n^s = (u_n^s, b_n^s, z_n^s)$ where, at location index n , $u_n^s \in [0, u_{\max}]$ is the
 231 great-circle distance in meters between the receiver and the source, $b_n^s \in [0^\circ, 360^\circ)$ is the bearing
 232 of the AUV with respect to the receiver (i.e., the angle at which the receiver sees the source, mea-

233 sured clockwise from due north) and $z_n^s \in [z_{\min}^s, z_{\max}^s]$. We define the AUV's path as the ordered
 234 source location sequence $\{\mathbf{x}_1^s, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N_L}^s\}$.

235 The database of modeled CIRs set up by the receiver is computed at all points of a cylin-
 236 drical grid designed to span the ranges $\mathcal{U} = \{\delta_u, 2\delta_u, \dots, u_{\max}\}$, the bearing angles $\mathcal{B} =$
 237 $\{\delta_b, 2\delta_b, \dots, 360^\circ\}$, and the depth values $\mathcal{Z} = \{z_{\min}^s, z_{\min}^s + \delta z, \dots, z_{\max}^s\}$. The set of grid points is
 238 then defined as $\mathcal{G} = \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{Z}$, where we denote $\mathbf{g}_{u_i b_i z_i} \in \mathcal{G}$ as the i th grid point, $i = 1, \dots, |\mathcal{G}|$.
 239 This corresponds to the first box in Fig. 1.

240 C. AUV Location Estimation

241 For each grid point $\mathbf{g}_{u_i b_i z_i}$, the receiver models the expected CIR using a propagation model.
 242 For this purpose, we employ the Bellhop ray tracing software (see Ch. 3 in³⁷ and³⁸). Bellhop
 243 is an established solution to numerically solve pressure wave propagation equations by taking
 244 into account boundary conditions. In particular, Bellhop can factor in, among others: the SSP at
 245 multiple points throughout the water body section that joins the transmitter to the receiver; the
 246 relevant bathymetry in the area, including abrupt changes; the shape of surface waves; and the
 247 geo-acoustic properties of the sea bottom sediments. Bellhop has been used to model acoustic
 248 channels in different communication contexts, and served as the basis for more complex models
 249 (e.g., see^{39,40}). In our context, Bellhop yields accurate time-of-arrival information for each acoustic
 250 path, and sufficiently accurate complex amplitude information, so that the outcome of correlation
 251 operations can be trusted. We will show that Bellhop offers sufficiently reliable CIR modeling in
 252 a sea trial in Section V.

253 The output of Bellhop includes a list of expected multipath arrivals, along with their amplitude,
 254 phase, delay, and reception angle. Moreover, for each arrival, Bellhop reports the list of bottom and
 255 surface reflections it incurred. This information is employed to construct two modeled responses,
 256 namely a partial CIR $h_{u_i z_i}^{(1)}(t)$, containing only the specular and surface-reflected arrivals,¹ and the
 257 complete CIR $h_{u_i b_i z_i}^{(2)}(t)$. As the specular and surface-reflected arrivals are practically independent
 258 of the bearing of the AUV relative to the receiver, and rather depend only on the SSP, on u_i , and
 259 on z_i , the subscript b_i has been dropped in $h_{u_i z_i}^{(1)}(t)$.

260 From the modeled CIRs, the receiver obtains two separate fingerprints, $h_{u_i z_i}^{(1)}$ and $h_{u_i b_i z_i}^{(2)}$. When
 261 the source is at location \mathbf{x}_n , its emitted signal is received as

$$r_n(t) = \hat{h}_{u_n b_n z_n}(t) \otimes s(t) + \nu(t), \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{h}_{u_n b_n z_n}(t)$ is the CIR estimated from a received signal, $s(t)$ is the emitted signal waveform,
 $\nu(t)$ is the ambient noise, and \otimes denotes convolution. The receiver then computes

$$f_{u_i z_i}^{(1)} = h_{u_i z_i}^{(1)}(t) \otimes s(t) \quad (2a)$$

$$f_{u_j b_j z_j}^{(2)} = h_{u_j b_j z_j}^{(2)}(t) \otimes s(t), \quad (2b)$$

262 and matches $r_n(t)$ against the fingerprints $f_{u_i z_i}^{(1)}$ and $f_{u_j b_j z_j}^{(2)}$ corresponding to the grid points in \mathcal{G} as
 263 follows.

264 For each point $(u_i z_i)$ in the grid, we compute the normalized correlation

$$C_{u_i z_i}^{(1)}(n) = \frac{\int_0^{+\infty} r_n(t) f_{u_i z_i}^{(1)}(t - \tau) dt}{\left(\int_0^T r_n(t)^2 dt \int_0^{+\infty} f_{u_i z_i}^{(1)}(t)^2 dt \right)^{1/2}}, \quad (3)$$

265 where T is the signal's duration, and τ is the time epoch corresponding to the correlation maxi-
 266 mum. Note that in (3) we perform a normalized correlation to reduce sensitivity to CIRs character-

267 ized by different power attenuation. Define $\mathcal{M}^{(1)}(n)$ as the set of all pairs (u_j, z_j) corresponding
268 to those $C_{u_i z_i}^{(1)}(n)$ that exceed a certain threshold Θ_D , $\forall (u_i, z_i) \in \mathcal{G}$, where we set Θ_D , using the
269 analysis in⁴². We remark that we do not limit set $\mathcal{M}^{(1)}(n)$ to contain just the coordinates of the
270 single grid point yielding the maximum correlation. In fact, at this point, the estimation of the
271 correct distance and depth may be hindered by the lack of, e.g., the specular arrival, which can
272 occur in the presence of SSP patterns with a sufficiently steep gradient and for a sufficiently large
273 distance between the AUV and the receiver (e.g., see the example on page 46 of Bellhop's man-
274 ual³⁸). Including a number of possible matching locations is more robust against such errors. The
275 above steps correspond to boxes 2 and 3 in Fig. 1.

276 For each $(u_j, z_j) \in \mathcal{M}^{(1)}(n)$, and $\forall b \in \mathcal{B}$, we compute the following normalized correlations:

$$C_{u_j b_j z_j}^{(2)}(n, \tau) = \frac{\int_0^{+\infty} r_n(t) f_{u_j b_j z_j}^{(2)}(t - \tau) dt}{\left(\int_0^T r_n(t)^2 dt \int_0^{+\infty} f_{u_j b_j z_j}^{(2)}(t)^2 dt \right)^{1/2}}. \quad (4)$$

277 Call

$$\rho_{\mathbf{x}_j}^n = \max_{\tau} C_{u_j b_j z_j}^{(2)}(n, \tau), \quad (5)$$

278 and define $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)$ as the set of all triples $\mathbf{p}_k = (u_k, b_k, z_k)$ corresponding to the $R^{(2)}$ highest
279 values of $\rho_{\mathbf{p}_k}^n$ $\forall (u_j, z_j) \in \mathcal{M}^{(1)}(n)$ and $\forall b \in \mathcal{B}$, where $R^{(2)}$ is a user-defined parameter (in our
280 performance evaluation, we set $R^{(2)} = 70$). The above steps correspond to boxes 4 and 5 in Fig. 1.

281 In ideal conditions, e.g., with an extremely dense grid \mathcal{G} , in the absence of noise, and with
282 perfect environmental information, it would be enough to limit set $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)$ to the coordinates
283 of the point $\mathbf{p}_k = (u_k, b_k, z_k)$ for which $\rho_{\mathbf{p}_k}^n$ is highest. However, in any practical scenario, the
284 grid point closest to the actual position of the AUV might not yield the highest correlation due
285 to noise, outdated environmental information, or a combination of both. In this perspective, it is

286 convenient to set $R^{(2)}$ to some large value. On the other hand, it is computationally infeasible to
 287 have an exceedingly large set \mathcal{G} . For this reason, we reduce the complexity of the search whenever
 288 possible by limiting the location search area through a bound on the distance between the AUV
 289 and the receiver. For example, if the source level is known, this bound can be obtained based on
 290 a received signal strength indicator (RSSI) as in⁴³. Furthermore, in the following we present a
 291 filtering scheme that reduces the complexity of path estimation.

292 **D. AUV Path Estimation**

293 After determining the possible matching locations $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)$ for $n = 1, \dots, N_L$, we proceed to
 294 find the most likely sequence of AUV's locations among all possible options using a path estima-
 295 tion algorithm. Without prior information about the AUV motion pattern, we avoid assuming a
 296 dynamic model solved by filtering, but rather work on a trellis such as the one shown in Fig. 4.
 297 The trellis has N_L stages, one for each transmission received from the AUV. In each stage, dif-
 298 ferent nodes represent different estimated locations, so that the first stage of the trellis represents
 299 all location estimates for the first detected signal from the AUV (set $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(1)$), the second stage
 300 contains the estimates in set $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(2)$, and so forth until the last stage, which contains the esti-
 301 mates in $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(N_L)$. We assign a confidence index to each node in the trellis (the value of the
 302 normalized cross-correlation between the modeled and measured channels, see (5)), and orga-
 303 nize them into a $R^{(2)} \times N_L$ matrix \mathbf{T} (boxes 6 and 7 in Fig. 1). Both the nodes in the i th trellis
 304 stage and the entries in the i th column of \mathbf{T} are sorted in order of decreasing confidence, i.e.,
 305 $[\mathbf{T}]_{1,i} = \rho_{\mathbf{p}_1}^i, [\mathbf{T}]_{2,i} = \rho_{\mathbf{p}_2}^i, [\mathbf{T}]_{R^{(2)},i} = \rho_{\mathbf{p}_{R^{(2)}}}^i$, and

$$\rho_{\mathbf{p}_1}^i > \rho_{\mathbf{p}_2}^i > \dots > \rho_{\mathbf{p}_{R^{(2)}}}^i. \quad (6)$$

FIG. 4. Example of trellis employed by the tracking algorithm for the source path estimation. Each node represents a location estimate. Trellis links exist only among locations that are closer than the maximum distance d_{\max} covered by the AUV when traveling at full speed between subsequent signal transmissions.

1. Setting the Path Weights

The objective of path estimation is to find the best sequence of nodes across consecutive trellis stages. To that end, a link exists between an entry in stage n and an entry in stage $n + 1$ if the locations represented by these nodes are closer than the maximum distance the AUV could cover when traveling at full speed v_{\max}^s between the n th and the $(n + 1)$ th signal detections (recall that the maximum absolute speed is assumed to be known). Formally, call $e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}$ the edge that connects the ℓ_n th node at stage n in the trellis (entry in column n of \mathbf{T}) and the ℓ_{n+1} th entry at column $n + 1$. Call $A(e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}) = \mathbf{p}_{\ell_n}$ and $S(e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}) = \mathbf{p}_{\ell_{n+1}}$ the ancestor and the successor of edge $e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}$, respectively. Define the edge weight as

$$\sigma(e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } d(\mathbf{p}_{\ell_n}, \mathbf{p}_{\ell_{n+1}}) \leq d_{\max} \\ \frac{d_{\max}}{d(\mathbf{p}_{\ell_n}, \mathbf{p}_{\ell_{n+1}})}, & \text{if } d_{\max} < d(\mathbf{p}_{\ell_n}, \mathbf{p}_{\ell_{n+1}}) \leq 1.5 d_{\max} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

315 where $d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|_2$ is the Euclidean distance between locations \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} , t_n and t_{n+1} are the
 316 reception epochs of the n th and $(n+1)$ th detected signals, respectively, and $d_{\max} = v_{\max}^s(t_{n+1} - t_n)$
 317 is the maximum distance that the AUV could have traveled between time epochs t_n and t_{n+1} . Only
 318 edges with non-zero weights are considered for path estimation. To form a continuous path, we
 319 require connected edges. In particular, if for edge $e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}$ it occurs that its ancestor \mathbf{p}_{ℓ_n} is not
 320 successor of any edge $e_{\ell_{n-1} \ell_n}$, or that its successor $\mathbf{p}_{\ell_{n+1}}$ is not ancestor of any edge $e_{\ell_{n+1}, \ell_{n+2}}$,
 321 then the weight of edge $e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}$ is set as zero, and the edge is removed from the trellis.

322 We remark the similarities between the path estimation algorithm and the Viterbi algorithm for
 323 tracking within a trellis (see also⁴⁴). While the Viterbi algorithm would yield the optimal solution,
 324 it would include all grid points in \mathcal{G} in each stage of the trellis. This would require $|\mathcal{G}|$ entries in
 325 each column of \mathbf{T} , which would compound to a huge state space and imply an exceedingly high
 326 computational complexity, especially if $|\mathcal{G}|$ is very large. In addition, solving through the Viterbi
 327 algorithm would require an estimation for the emission and transition probabilities, which involves
 328 some hard assumptions on the CIR and noise models. Instead, our version relies on confidence
 329 indices, and makes it possible to trim the state space according to physical movement constraints.
 330 This leads to a significant performance improvement and to a feasible path estimation complexity.

331 2. Finding the Best Path

332 Let $\mathcal{E}(n) = \{e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}\}$ be the set of edges that link a node in stage n of the trellis to a node in
 333 stage $n + 1$, and use (7) to define the following metric for each edge

$$\lambda(e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}) = \rho_{\mathbf{p}_{\ell_n}}^n \rho_{\mathbf{p}_{\ell_{n+1}}}^{n+1} \sigma(e_{\ell_n \ell_{n+1}}), \quad (8)$$

334 where the confidence indices are taken from \mathbf{T} . Define a generic path on the trellis as

$$\Psi = \{e_1, \dots, e_{N_L}\}, \quad (9)$$

335 where e_i is a shorthand for $e_{\ell_i \ell_{i+1}} \in \mathcal{E}(i)$, and all edges are such that $S(e_i) = A(e_{i+1})$, $i =$
 336 $1, \dots, N_L - 1$. Define the overall path metric as

$$\Lambda(\Psi) = \frac{\prod_{i=1}^{N_L-1} \lambda(e_i)}{\prod_{i=1}^{N_L-2} \rho_{S(e_i)}^i}, \quad (10)$$

337 i.e., as the product of the confidence metrics for all edges that belong to the path, divided by the
 338 confidence of intermediate nodes in order to avoid accounting for them twice. The path estimate
 339 is finally found as

$$\hat{\Psi} = \arg \max_{\Psi} \Lambda(\Psi), \quad (11)$$

340 and we indicate the sequence of locations traversed by $\hat{\Psi}$ as $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_1, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{N_L}\}$.

341 As a means of measuring the discrepancy between the true and the estimated sequence of
 342 AUV's locations, we consider the root mean square (RMS) point-wise distance between corre-
 343 sponding points of the true and estimated paths. Formally,

$$\varepsilon_{\hat{\Psi}}^d = \left(\frac{1}{N_L} \sum_{n=1}^{N_L} d(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_n, \mathbf{x}_n^s)^2 \right)^{1/2}. \quad (12)$$

344 We also convey the source bearing estimation effectiveness of our approach via the bearing error

$$\varepsilon_{\hat{\Psi}}^a = \frac{1}{N_L} \sum_{n=1}^{N_L} |\hat{b}_n - b_n^s|, \quad (13)$$

345 where $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the distance between two points in the cylindrical coordinate system.

3. Refinement

In this section, we present two refinements to the above algorithm. The first refinement relates to the possible case that there exists no edge with a non-zero weight connecting two trellis stages n and $n + 1$. This would lead to a partitioning of the trellis. We correct for these cases by allowing stage $n - 1$ to directly connect to stage $n + 1$. Specifically, the corresponding edge $e_{\ell_{n-1}\ell_{n+1}}$ will have a weight equal to

$$\lambda(e_{\ell_{n-1}\ell_{n+1}}) = \rho_{\mathbf{P}^{\ell_{n-1}}}^{n-1} \rho_{\mathbf{P}^{\ell_{n+1}}}^{n+1} \sigma(e_{\ell_{n-1}\ell_{n+1}}), \quad (14)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the same as in (7).

The above recovery mechanism is further enhanced to handle cases of broader trellis partitioning due to bursts of errors. These bursts are caused by strong noise from, e.g., a nearby vessel or waves, or due to erroneous bathymetry information at some locations. The result of such bursts are sets of short paths for which the maximization in (11) is not optimal, i.e., the problem becomes non-convex. Considering this case, we increase the number of paths in Ψ through our second refinement procedure as follows.

We start by observing that, from the perspective of path finding, we can calculate paths by taking sets of estimated locations either in order they occur in time, or by reversing this order. In other words, the trellis stages in Fig. 4 and the corresponding columns in \mathbf{T} can be flipped, such that the first contains location estimates in $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(N_L)$, the second contains the estimates in $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(N_L - 1)$, and so forth until the last column, which contains the samples in $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(1)$. Call Ψ_F a forward path on the trellis traversing locations $\{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N_L}\}$, and call Ψ_B a backward path computed on the reversed trellis, traversing locations $\{\mathbf{y}_{N_L}, \mathbf{y}_{N_L-1}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{N_1}\}$. If $\hat{\Psi}_F$ and $\hat{\Psi}_B$ are the best forward and backward paths according to (11), respectively, we set the final path estimate

367 $\hat{\Psi} = \hat{\Psi}_F$ if $\Lambda(\hat{\Psi}_F) > \Lambda(\hat{\Psi}_B)$, and $\hat{\Psi} = \hat{\Psi}_B$ otherwise. In case of significant interruptions in the
368 trellis structure, the above scheme increases the probability to find the correct path. The scheme
369 is also beneficial if the estimate of the initial location on the forward path is incorrect, making the
370 path search diverge to a mostly wrong sequence of locations. In case of a well connected trellis,
371 instead, the scheme is likely to find the same path twice, with no effect on the accuracy of the
372 algorithm.

373 The complexity of the algorithm relates to the number of correlation operations and to the
374 trellis search. For each received source signal, the algorithm computes $\kappa|\mathcal{G}| + \mathcal{O}(|\mathcal{M}^{(1)}(n)|) \approx$
375 $\kappa|\mathcal{G}|$ correlations in order to extract the possible position estimates in set $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)$, where κ is a
376 proportionality factor that account for the search space reduction enabled, e.g., by RSSI bounding
377 considerations as mentioned in Section III C. For a signal of bandwidth–time duration product BT ,
378 the complexity of each normalized cross correlation is $\mathcal{O}(B^2)$. With $\mathcal{O}(N_L|\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)|)$ operations
379 for the trellis search, the overall complexity is $\mathcal{O}(N_L|\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)| + |\mathcal{G}|B^2)$. Comparing this with
380 the complexity of the Viterbi algorithm, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(N_L|\mathcal{G}|^2)$ (see also³²), a significant complexity
381 reduction exists.

382 E. Discussion

383 Our method considers the practical case of observing an unknown target. This target can move
384 in any dynamic pattern and even irregularly. Hence, we avoid evaluating its position through
385 filtering, and rather follow a trellis search approach over the confidence indices. This also means
386 that the path found from all feasible solutions is the one with maximum overall confidence index,
387 and thus isolated positions associated to a high confidence value will not be chosen. This is

388 appropriate, since we are looking for a systematic solution, rather than an individual match. Our
389 solution for the trellis search takes a suboptimal approach by taking into account sets of only two
390 nodes. This has the drawback that a single node in the trellis may have a higher impact than it
391 should. Yet, without prior knowledge of the target and to keep the calculations feasible we avoid
392 other solutions in the form of, e.g., dynamic programming. Further, we note that the accuracy of
393 our method depends on the quality of the channel estimation process, which improves with the
394 bandwidth of the emitted signal.

395 For channel modeling, we use the bathymetry and the sound speed profile. Without up-to-date
396 information about instantaneous sea conditions, we avoid a time-varying propagation model and
397 use instead a static model. Instead, the time-variation of the channel is taken into account by the
398 AUV's motion, both by calculating different channels for different locations, and by using the
399 maximum velocity v_{\max}^s . This parameter trades off complexity with performance, as higher values
400 for the maximum speed corresponds to additional possible paths in the considered trellis. Another
401 significant assumption is the ability to estimate the channel from the received signals. Clearly
402 the performance of our approach depends on the accuracy of such estimation. While channel
403 estimation is beyond the scope of this work, possible techniques for such an estimation can be
404 rake receivers⁴⁵, blind source separation⁴⁶, or cyclo-stationary analysis⁴⁷, to name a few options.

405 IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

406 A. Scenario and Parameters

407 For our simulations, we consider a portion of the San Diego bay area, off the coast of US's
408 southern California, which is a well-explored area. We place the receiver at the coordinates

409 [32.9390°N, 117.2816°W]. We take the area’s bathymetry data from the US Coastal Relief
 410 model⁴⁸ (revealing that the average depth in the area is about 50 m), and employ an SSP sample
 411 taken at the observed area. The SSP has a downward-refractive shape, typical of shallow Cali-
 412 fornian waters during warm seasons, as depicted in Fig. 2b. We assume that the water surface is
 413 flat.

414 In our simulations, we deploy both the receiver and the source at depths of 10 m. Still, we
 415 remark that the receiver is not aware of the source’s depth. The simulation starts by deploying
 416 the emitting source at random in the area at a range of 500 m from the receiver. The source then
 417 chooses a bearing uniformly at random and moves along the corresponding direction with constant
 418 speed chosen at random for the time required to carry out 10 transmissions. The locations \mathbf{x}_n^s
 419 and \mathbf{x}_{n+1}^s , where two subsequent emissions take place, are chosen uniformly at random such that
 420 $d(\mathbf{x}_n^s, \mathbf{x}_{n+1}^s) \leq d_{\max}$, and we set $d_{\max} = 50$ m.

421 The fingerprint grid pre-computed by the receiver spans a total range $u_{\max} = 1.5$ km around
 422 the receiver, with a resolution of 1 m. The whole azimuthal plane is considered, with a resolution
 423 of 1°, and the CIRs are computed for all depths between 5 m and 15 m, also with a resolution of
 424 1 m. This choice leads to a total of about 6 million points in set \mathcal{G} , and emphasizes the need for
 425 our path finding algorithm, as it has much lower complexity than the regular Viterbi algorithm.

426 The signal transmitted by the source, $s(t)$, is chosen to be a linear chirp signal of duration
 427 100 ms and bandwidth of 10 kHz, centered at a carrier frequency of 12 kHz. Based on these
 428 signal parameters and using the analysis in⁴², for the computation of (3) and the formation of set
 429 $\mathcal{M}^{(1)}(n)$, we choose $\Theta_D = 0.1 \forall n$. For each emission from a given source-receiver location pairs,
 430 the channel impulse response is computed through Bellhop³⁸, using as parameters the SSP and the

FIG. 5. Example of correlation values for $\mathbf{x}^s = [446 \text{ m}, 150^\circ, 10 \text{ m}]$ at an SNR of 30 dB, for different value of the offset Δz between the actual depth and the tested depth.

431 available bathymetry samples along the direction from the source to the receiver. The ambient
 432 noise at the receiver is modeled as an additive white Gaussian process, whose power is tuned so as
 433 to achieve a prescribed signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

434 B. Examples

435 A sample result from (3) is shown in Fig. 5a. We observe a clear peak suggesting that the
 436 source is located at a distance of approximately 450 m from the receiver, at a depth of 10 m. This
 437 is due to the presence of all expected specular and surface-reflected arrivals in the received signal.
 438 If, e.g., the specular arrival were missing, the correlation peak at 450 m would not be as high. This
 439 is why we consider all three significant peaks, including those at about 300 m and 600 m, and for
 440 all depths where such peaks exceed Θ_D .

FIG. 6. Accuracy of the path estimation algorithm in the presence of exact environmental data, for different values of the SNR. Even for low values of the SNR the arrival structure in the CIRs does not change considerably, and has no significant effects on performance.

441 To populate set $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)$, we set $R^{(2)} = 70$. A sample computation of (4) for some range-depth
 442 pairs in $\mathcal{M}^{(1)}(n)$ is shown in Fig. 5b. While in this particular case a peak stands out corresponding
 443 to the correct bearing of about 150° , often such a favorable result does not occur. The chosen
 444 value of $R^{(2)}$ makes it possible to considerably increase the probability that the actual bearing is
 445 included in $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)$, while keeping the computational effort controlled.

446 C. Localization Accuracy Under Varying SNR

447 We start our performance evaluation by running our algorithm in the presence of exact envi-
 448 ronmental data under different SNR values. The complementary cumulative distribution functions
 449 (CCDFs) of the root mean square error (RMSE) affecting the distance and bearing estimates are

450 shown in Figs. 6a and 6b, respectively. Thanks to the perfect knowledge of both the bathymetry
451 and the SSP in the observed area, neither result shows a significant dependence on the SNR, even
452 after decreasing it to as low as 3 dB, which tends to make additional peaks appear in the correlation
453 outputs. We observe that the average RMSE varies from about 120 m for an SNR of 30 dB, up to
454 about 170 m for an SNR of 3 dB, with a median error around 80 m, which is satisfactory given the
455 grid resolution employed and the use of a single receiving element. The bearing estimation results
456 show even higher accuracy, with a mean estimation error $\varepsilon_a < 20^\circ$ even for an SNR of 3 dB, and
457 a median error of less than 10° .

458 **D. Localization Accuracy Under Imperfect Bathymetry Data**

459 The above simulation results show accurate localization for different SNR levels. However,
460 the results are obtained assuming perfect bathymetry and sound speed profile knowledge. In our
461 setting, the receiver is an anchored station, e.g., a marine observatory, and thus we argue that
462 accurate sound speed measurements are possible and do often exist in such marine observatories
463 (e.g., see⁴⁹). Still, while fine-gridded bathymetry mapping can be made around the observatory,
464 small errors and outdated measurements in the resulting depth map may exist. We now explore
465 the sensitivity of our localization method to imperfect bathymetry information.

466 In the following analysis, to each true bathymetry sample we add an offset drawn uniformly
467 at random in the interval $[-y, y]$, where y (in m) is a tunable parameter. We collect a Monte-
468 Carlo set of 100 source paths and compute the CCDFs of the RMSE for both the distance and the
469 bearing. The results are shown in Figs. 7a and 7b, respectively. We observe that, as expected,
470 mismatched bathymetry data worsens the path estimation performance. However, for a limited

FIG. 7. Accuracy of the path estimation algorithm in the presence of imperfect bathymetry data. Erroneous bathymetry significantly affects the algorithm’s performance. For limited errors ($y = 1$ m) the results are still viable for several applications.

471 offset on bathymetry samples, up to $y = 1$ m, the median RMS distance error remains below
 472 200 m (or 6% of the total observed area), which is still a reasonably good result given the presence
 473 of a single receiving element. Instead, an error of up to $y = 5$ m yields comparatively worse
 474 performance. However, we remark that this is an extreme case, as such an error amounts to about
 475 10% of the average sea bottom depth in the area, and current sea bottom mapping systems typically
 476 ensure sub-meter bathymetry measurements for depths of less than 200 m (e.g., this is the case for
 477 Kongsberg Maritime’s 400 kHz EM 2040 multibeam sonar system we use in our sea experiment).

478 Similar conclusions as for the distance-based sensitivity of the algorithm can be drawn also for
 479 the bearing estimation error. Fig. 7b shows that for $y = 1$ m, the increase in the median bearing
 480 estimation error is roughly 20° , and increases to roughly 55° for $y = 5$ m. This result emphasizes

FIG. 8. Accuracy of the path estimation algorithm in the presence of imperfect SSP data. Increasing deviations from the actual SSP tend to significantly change the multipath arrival structure. For limited deviations, the median localization and angle error remain acceptable.

481 the need for accurate bathymetry information. Still, we argue that even such rough localization
 482 estimates can be instrumental for some applications. For example, security or environmental mon-
 483 itoring systems, where even a rough estimate can trigger a more accurate investigation by human
 484 personnel or more complex detection mechanisms; or fauna and habitat monitoring applications,
 485 where it is often sufficient to find the approximate path of a vocalizing animal.

486 E. Localization Accuracy Under Imperfect SSP Data

487 In order to evaluate the impact of imperfect SSP data on the performance of our algorithm, we
488 add an offset drawn uniformly at random in the interval $[-c, c]$ to each true SSP sample, and carry
489 out Monte-Carlo simulations for different value of c .

490 The CCDFs of the distance and bearing RMSE are provided in in Figs. 8a and 8b, respectively.
491 While the chosen values for c preserve the general downward-refractive properties of the SSP,
492 even a small value tends to cause significant changes in the structure of multipath arrivals. For
493 $c = 0.25$ m/s, we already observe a median distance error of about 250 m and a median bearing
494 error of about 30° . It could be argued that these values are still practical for rough localization
495 applications, where the only need is to know whether the AUV is practically following a desired
496 trajectory or is falling significantly off track. As expected, increasing c tends to reduce both the
497 distance and the bearing estimation accuracy. This emphasizes the need to maintain SSP estimates
498 updated at the receiver, and to recompute the CIRs in the grid \mathcal{G} in the presence of significant
499 changes.

500 We finally remark that, besides bathymetry and SSP, high sea states may induce significant
501 surface waves that would also contribute to modifying surface-reflected multipath components of
502 the modeled and measured CIRs. Since it is not feasible to create different modeled CIR sets \mathcal{G}
503 for many realizations of the surface waves and for different sea states, in this case it would be
504 appropriate to skip the correlation-based depth/distance estimation that results in sets $\mathcal{M}^{(1)}(n)$.
505 Instead, it would be possible to populate $\mathcal{M}^{(1)}(n)$ with all pairs of depth and distance values that

FIG. 9. Comparison among different location estimation schemes: our algorithm, the preliminary version of our approach in¹, and the best point benchmark (corresponding to selecting the location that yields the highest cross-correlation value).

506 satisfy RSSI bounds, and then proceed with the computation of the cross-correlations that lead to
 507 set $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)$.

508 F. Comparison against benchmark localization schemes

509 We conclude our evaluation with a comparison among our algorithm, its preliminary version
 510 in¹, and a benchmark scheme that, for every location index n corresponding to a signal received by
 511 the buoy, chooses the most likely source location as the grid point in $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(n)$ yielding the largest
 512 correlation value (dubbed “best point” in the following). This is akin to a classical fingerprint-
 513 based localization approach, where the fingerprint is defined as the value of (4). Fig. 9 shows the

514 CCDFs of the distance and bearing RMSE for all above approaches carrying out all operations
515 listed in Section III, including the forward-backward refinement of Section III D 3.

516 The results confirm the expectation that our approach achieves a lower estimation error. This
517 is also due to the forward-backward search refinement, which reduces the chance that a com-
518 paratively low correlation value in the first point of the source’s trajectory hampers the correct
519 estimation of the whole path. Specifically, the median distance RMSE decreases from about 100
520 to about 50 m, in the presence of a comparable angle RMSE. Although the best point scheme
521 provides a good estimation of the bearing in these simulations, its distance error is still very sig-
522 nificant, with 80% of the errors being greater than 100 m. Moreover, while the tail of the error
523 distribution for the best point scheme is better than for the algorithms in¹ and in this paper, these
524 tails already correspond to significant errors (e.g., > 300 m in terms of distance and $> 45^\circ$ in terms
525 of bearing).

526 V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

527 A. Experiment Setup

528 In the previous section, we explored the performance of our localization scheme in simulations.
529 Since these simulations rely heavily on a numerical acoustic propagation model, we now complete
530 our analysis and show the performance achieved by our algorithm in a sea trial. The experiment
531 was carried out in February 2017 in northern Israel (coordinates $33^\circ 01' 57.0''$ N $34^\circ 55' 41.2''$ E), in
532 waters with a maximum depth of 140 m. The measured sound speed was 1529 m/s with a water
533 temperature of 21° Celsius at the sea surface, and 1521 m/s with a water temperature of 17° Celsius

(a) Contour bathymetry map of the sea experiment area.

(b) Spectrogram of the received signals.

FIG. 10. Setup of the sea experiment carried out in Mediterranean Sea waters near Haifa, Israel, in Feb. 2017.

534 at the sea bottom. The sound speed gradient between the surface and bottom was approximately
 535 constant. the current at the water surface was roughly 0.5 knot, the wave height was roughly 40 cm,
 536 and the sea bottom was sandy. A 5 m-resolution bathymetry was collected using a Kongsberg EM
 537 2040 400 kHz multibeam sonar. The bathymetry of the explored area is shown in Fig. 10a, and
 538 included a steep slope ranging from 60 m to 140 m. The top-left side of the figure shows artificial
 539 data as no measurements were collected in that region.

540 The experiment included an 80-foot long vessel, RV EDEN, and a 13 feet rubber boat dragging
 541 a floating buoy from which an acoustic emitter was deployed, see Fig. 11. The rubber boat repre-
 542 sented the opportunistic sounds source, and the RV EDEN represented the single receiver. During
 543 the transmissions, the distance between the vessels was roughly 1200 m. The transmissions from
 544 the rubber boat included a sequence of 15 linear chirps at the frequency range of 7 kHz to 17 kHz,

FIG. 11. Picture of the buoy and ship from which the transmitter and receiver were deployed, respectively.

545 each of duration of 1 s. Transmissions were made with the EvoLogics S2C R 7/17W underwa-
546 ter acoustic software defined modem at a source level of 170 dB re $1\mu\text{Pa}$ @1m. Receptions at
547 the RV EDEN were made through the custom uRadar recorder, whose receive sensitivity at the
548 transmissions' frequency range is about 190 dBV re $1\mu\text{Pa}$. Both the transmitter and the receiver
549 were deployed at depth of 10 m. A time-frequency spectrogram of the received signals is shown
550 in Fig. 10b. Besides the transmitted chirp signals, we observe the signals of the RV EDEN's own
551 echo-sounder. To mitigate the ambient noise as well as the signals of the echo-sounder, we filtered
552 each chirp signal. Synchronization was performed using a normalized matched filter⁴².

FIG. 12. Sequence of location estimates for nine subsequent transmissions from a drifting source in the sea experiment, showing the true location of the source (green cross), the estimate of our algorithm (red triangles), the best point benchmark estimates (purple triangles), the Kalman filter results (grey squares), and the limited-scope Viterbi estimates (blue triangles).

553 B. Results

554 We start from Figs. 12 and 14, which detail the results of the comparison between the modeled
555 CIRs and the measured one for nine consecutive received signals. The results are shown as a polar
556 map centered around the location of the RV EDEN, where each contour line represents a distance
557 of 300 m from the vessel. In Fig. 12, each small grey cross represents a possible position for the
558 source, i.e., a comparison output that passed the detection threshold Θ_D (see Section III C) and
559 was included in set $\mathcal{M}^{(2)}(i)$, $i = 1, \dots, 9$. The thicker green cross marks the true location of
560 the source. We observe that, for each of the nine received signals, many possible locations are
561 obtained as a result of the cross-correlation operations carried out by our method. Fig. 13 shows
562 one comparison between a CIR measured from a received signal and the CIR template constructed
563 starting from Bellhop’s output (light blue) and corresponding to a location close to the true location
564 of the source. We observe that although the channel model is imperfect, all significant peaks in the
565 measured CIR are well represented, leading to a good overall matching. However, other locations
566 also lead to a similarly strong matching, resulting in several location estimates being significantly
567 far from the source, and collectively resembling a random cloud of possible source locations (the
568 small grey crosses). The best point algorithm (purple triangle), that points to the location yielding
570 the maximum correlation for each signal, suffers from significant errors in three cases out of nine.
571 These results support the simulation outcomes, showing that even when the bathymetry is fully
572 known, relying only on the spatial diversity of the channel impulse response yields significant
573 residual uncertainty. Processing the outcome of the best point algorithm through a Kalman filter
574 does not yield significantly better results, even if the filter is fed with the actual velocity of the
575 AUV (in contrast with our approach, that only requires to know the maximum AUV velocity,

FIG. 13. Comparison between a template CIR obtained from Bellhop (light blue) and the CIR measured from a signal received during the sea experiment.

576 v_{\max}^s). The corresponding location estimates are shown in Fig. 13 as grey squares. Conversely,
 577 our algorithm (red triangles) exploits the trellis search to achieve a more precise estimation and
 578 removes outliers, resulting in a much smaller localization error.

579 We also compare the above results against those of the Viterbi algorithm. Given the size of
 580 the state space, in order to be able to run the algorithm we artificially reduce the search scope to
 581 a 90° sector centered on the true bearing of the source, and to the distances ranging from 1000
 582 to 1400 m. While this gives a clear advantage to the Viterbi algorithm, it is a necessary step to
 583 allow the search space to fit in its data structures. The Viterbi results are shown as blue triangles
 584 in Fig. 12. We observe that the algorithm correctly predicts the fact that the source is static, but
 585 achieves a slightly worse location error despite the limitation of the search scope. This outcome

FIG. 14. Final drifting source path estimate in the sea experiment, showing the true location of the source (green cross), the estimate of our algorithm (red triangles), the best point benchmark estimates (purple triangles), the Kalman filter results (grey squares), and the limited-scope Viterbi estimates (blue triangles). The total localization error for our algorithm is between 174 m (5.8%) and 330 m (11%), with a bearing error between 2 and 12 degrees.

586 is due to systematic, non-Gaussian errors incurred when modeling real underwater propagation
 587 using an acoustic propagation model under imperfect information (e.g., in this case, the resolution
 588 of the bathymetry and SSP data).

589 We summarize the path estimation results for the comparison outputs in Fig. 12 are shown 14
 590 with the same color coding as above. In this case, the green crosses represent the average location
 591 of the drifting RV EDEN throughout the experiment. The results show a nice match between the

592 estimated location and the true one for our algorithm and the Viterbi algorithm, and for only a
593 subset of the location estimates of the best point algorithm. The Kalman filter results also show
594 that this method is very sensitive to incorrect estimates of the initial location of the AUV.

595 The estimated locations predicted by our approach also correctly follow the drifting direction
596 of the source boat. The total localization error for our algorithm is between 174 m and 330 m,
597 with a bearing error between 2 and 12 degrees. While these errors may seem large, we argue that
598 for the task of localizing an AUV in a long term mission, this is still acceptable. This is because,
599 first, after a few hours especially in deep water, the self-navigation system of the AUV completely
600 drifts and thus any localization solution of limited expected error will benefit the operation⁵⁰, and
601 second, compared to the typical detection range of roughly 5 km for the AUV's pinger (e.g.,⁵¹), the
602 above reported localization error as in our experiment is still a good result. Given that this result
603 was obtained using only one receiver in real sea conditions, it demonstrates well the applicability
604 of our suggested localization method.

605 VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

606 In this paper, we presented a novel approach for the acoustic localization of a non-cooperating
607 AUV emitting acoustic signals. Our approach relies on a single passive and stationary receiving
608 element and on the modeling of acoustic propagation given knowledge of the bathymetry, sound
609 speed profile and bottom sediments in the deployment area. The method is based on the compari-
610 son of a channel impulse response evaluated from a received acoustic signal, against a database of
611 channel impulse response fingerprints. As the latter are modeled instead of measured, we require
612 no periodic channel fingerprint acquisition in the area around the receiver. To filter noise, locations

613 that show a good match between the measured and the modeled channels are arranged into a trellis.
614 A location path is then estimated while limiting transitions between the trellis nodes according to
615 an assumed maximum velocity for the AUV. Our approach makes it possible to estimate the path
616 traveled by the AUV with low complexity and with high accuracy. Such accuracy decreases (but
617 still remains sufficient for a variety of applications) if the receiver holds outdated environmental
618 data. A proof-of-concept sea experiment demonstrates the applicability of our method to real sea
619 conditions with a localization error as low as 5.8%, which is a remarkably good accuracy given the
620 use of a single stationary receiver and the realistic imperfect bathymetry and sound speed profile
621 measurements.

622 Future work will include a refinement considering a finer non-uniform grid in locations where
623 the input data shows the largest variability, as well as extending the localization to multiple targets.

624 REFERENCES

625 ¹E. Dubrovinskaya, R. Diamant, and P. Casari, “Anchorless underwater acoustic localization,” in
626 *Proc. IEEE WPNC*, Bremen, Germany (2017).

627 ²J. J. Leonard and A. Bahr, “Autonomous underwater vehicle navigation,” in *Handbook of Ocean*
628 *Engineering* (Springer, 2016), pp. 341–358.

629 ³Z. Zhou, Z. Peng, J.-H. Cui, Z. Shi, and A. Bagtzoglou, “Scalable localization with mobility
630 prediction for underwater sensor networks,” *IEEE Trans. Mobile Comput.* **10**(3), 335–348 (2011).

631 ⁴R. Diamant and L. Lampe, “Underwater localization with time-synchronization and propagation
632 speed uncertainties,” *IEEE Trans. Mobile Comput.* **12**(7), 1257–1269 (2013).

- 633 ⁵K.-C. Lee, J.-S. Ou, M.-C. Huang, and M.-C. Fang, “A novel location estimation based on pattern
634 matching algorithm in underwater environments,” *Applied Acoust.* **70**(3), 479–483 (2009).
- 635 ⁶H.-P. Tan, R. Diamant, W. K. Seah, and M. Waldmeyer, “A survey of techniques and challenges
636 in underwater localization,” *Ocean Eng.* **38**(14), 1663–1676 (2011).
- 637 ⁷L. Paull, S. Saeedi, M. Seto, and H. Li, “AUV navigation and localization: A review,” *IEEE J.*
638 *Ocean. Eng.* **39**(1), 131–149 (2014).
- 639 ⁸J. Reis, M. Morgado, P. Batista, P. Oliveira, and C. Silvestre, “Design and experimental valida-
640 tion of a usbl underwater acoustic positioning system,” *Sensors* **16**(9) (2016) [https://www.
641 mdpi.com/1424-8220/16/9/1491](https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/16/9/1491).
- 642 ⁹M. Erol-Kantarci, H. Mouftah, and S. Oktug, “Localization techniques for underwater acoustic
643 sensor networks,” *IEEE Commun. Mag.* **48**(12), 152–158 (2010).
- 644 ¹⁰S. Gezici, “A survey on wireless position estimation,” *Wireless Pers. Commun.* **44**(3), 263–282
645 (2008).
- 646 ¹¹Z. Zhang, C. L. Law, and Y. L. Guan, “Modified phase-only correlator with kurtosis-based
647 amplified-noise suppression,” *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.* **9**(11), 3341–3345 (2010).
- 648 ¹²L. Mu, G. Kuo, and N. Tao, “A novel ToA location algorithm using LOS range estimation for
649 NLOS environments,” in *Proc. IEEE VTC*, Melbourne, Australia (2006).
- 650 ¹³J. Ash and R. Moses, “Acoustic time delay estimation and sensor network self-localization:
651 Experimental results,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **118**(2), 841–850 (2005).
- 652 ¹⁴D. McCrady, L. Doyle, H. Forstrom, T. Dempsey, and M. Martorana, “Mobile ranging using
653 low-accuracy clocks,” *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory and Techniques* **48**(6), 951–957 (2000).

- 654 ¹⁵S. Fischer, H. Grubeck, A. Kangas, H. Koorapaty, E. Larsson, and P. Lundqvist, “Time of arrival
655 estimation of narrowband TDMA signals for mobile positioning,” *Proc. IEEE PIMRC* 451–455
656 (1998).
- 657 ¹⁶E. Dubrovinskaya, I. Nissen, and P. Casari, “On the accuracy of passive multipath-aided under-
658 water range estimation,” in *Proc. UComms*, Lerici, Italy (2016).
- 659 ¹⁷C. O. Tiemann, M. B. Porter, and L. N. Frazer, “Localization of marine mammals near Hawaii
660 using an acoustic propagation model,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **115**(6), 2834–2843 (2004).
- 661 ¹⁸J. Gebbie, M. Siderius, and J. S. Allen III, “A two-hydrophone range and bearing localization
662 algorithm with performance analysis,” *J. Acoust. Soc. of America* **137**(3), 1586–1597 (2015).
- 663 ¹⁹A. B. Baggeroer, W. A. Kuperman, and P. N. Mikhalevsky, “An overview of matched field
664 methods in ocean acoustics,” *IEEE J. Ocean. Eng.* **18**(4), 401–424 (1993).
- 665 ²⁰J. S. Perkins and W. Kuperman, “Environmental signal processing: Three-dimensional matched-
666 field processing with a vertical array,” *J. Acoust. Soc. of America* **87**(4), 1553–1556 (1990).
- 667 ²¹K. L. Gemba, W. S. Hodgkiss, and P. Gerstoft, “Adaptive and compressive matched field pro-
668 cessing,” *J. Acoust. Soc. of America* **141**(1), 92–103 (2017).
- 669 ²²S. Shakeri and G. Leus, “Underwater ultra-wideband fingerprinting-based sparse localization,”
670 in *Proc. IEEE SPAWC*, Toronto, Canada (2014).
- 671 ²³S. Rakotonarivo and W. Kuperman, “Model-independent range localization of a moving source
672 in shallow water,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **132**(4), 2218–2223 (2012).
- 673 ²⁴C. M. Verlinden, J. Sarkar, B. D. Cornuelle, and W. A. Kuperman, “Determination of acoustic
674 waveguide invariant using ships as sources of opportunity in a shallow water marine environ-

- 675 ment,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **141**(2), EL102–EL107 (2017).
- 676 ²⁵L. Liao, Y. V. Zakharov, and P. D. Mitchell, “Underwater localization based on grid computation
677 and its application to transmit beamforming in multiuser UWA communications,” *IEEE Access*
678 **6**, 4297–4307 (2018).
- 679 ²⁶M. S. Ibn Seddik, L. Jaulin, and J. Grimsdale, “Phase based localization for underwater vehicles
680 using interval analysis,” *Mathematics in Computer Science* **8**(3), 495–502 (2014).
- 681 ²⁷H. Liu, H. Darabi, P. Banerjee, and J. Liu, “Survey of wireless indoor positioning techniques and
682 systems,” *IEEE Trans. Syst., Man, Cybern. C* **37**(6), 1067–1080 (2007).
- 683 ²⁸K. Kaemarungsi and P. Krishnamurthy, “Modeling of indoor positioning systems based on loca-
684 tion fingerprinting,” in *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, Hong Kong, China (2004), Vol. 2, pp. 1012–1022.
- 685 ²⁹Y. Jin, W. Soh, and W. Wong, “Indoor localization with channel impulse response based finger-
686 print and nonparametric regression,” *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.* **9**(3), 1120–1127 (2010).
- 687 ³⁰X. Guo and N. Ansari, “Localization by fusing a group of fingerprints via multiple antennas in
688 indoor environment,” *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.* **66**(11), 9904–9915 (2017).
- 689 ³¹P. Tseng, Y. Chan, Y. Lin, D. Lin, N. Wu, and T. Wang, “Ray-tracing-assisted fingerprinting
690 based on channel impulse response measurement for indoor positioning,” *IEEE Trans. Instrum.*
691 *Meas.* **66**(5), 1032–1045 (2017).
- 692 ³²N. Etemadyrad, “A sequential detection approach to indoor positioning using RSS-based finger-
693 printing,” Master’s thesis, George Mason University (2017).
- 694 ³³P. K. Yadav and W. Meng, “Mobile targets localization in a field area using moving gaussian
695 peaks and probability map,” in *Proc. IEEE ICCA*, Taichung, Taiwan (2014).

696 ³⁴Z. Xiao, H. Wen, A. Markham, and N. Trigoni, “Lightweight map matching for indoor localisa-
697 tion using conditional random fields,” in *Proc. IPSN*, Berlin, Germany (2014).

698 ³⁵Z. Wei, Y. Zhao, X. Liu, and Z. Feng, “DoA-LF: A location fingerprint positioning algorithm
699 with millimeter-wave,” *IEEE Access* **5**, 22678–22688 (2017).

700 ³⁶J. Palacios, G. Bielsa, P. Casari, and J. Widmer, “Single- and multiple-access point indoor local-
701 ization for millimeter-wave networks,” *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.* **18**(3), 1927–1942 (2019).

702 ³⁷F. Jensen, W. Kuperman, M. Porter, and H. Schmidt, *Computational Ocean Acoustics*, 2 ed.
703 (Springer-Verlag, New York, 1984).

704 ³⁸M. Porter *et al.*, “Bellhop code,” [http://oalib.hlsresearch.com/Rays/index.](http://oalib.hlsresearch.com/Rays/index.html)
705 [html](http://oalib.hlsresearch.com/Rays/index.html), Last time accessed: May 2018.

706 ³⁹P. Qarabaqi and M. Stojanovic, “Statistical characterization and computationally efficient mod-
707 eling of a class of underwater acoustic communication channels,” *IEEE J. Ocean. Eng.* **38**(4),
708 701–717 (2013).

709 ⁴⁰L. M. Wolff, E. Szczepanski, and S. Badri-Hoehner, “Acoustic underwater channel and network
710 simulator,” in *Proc. MTS/IEEE OCEANS*, Yeosu, Korea (2012), pp. 1–6.

711 ⁴¹Note that this information is part of Bellhop’s standard output data, and that we do not need to
712 track any propagation history analysis for any of the components of the measured CIR.

713 ⁴²R. Diamant, “Closed form analysis of the normalized matched filter with a test case for detection
714 of underwater acoustic signals,” *IEEE Access* **4**, 8225–8235 (2016) doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2016.2630498)
715 [2016.2630498](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2016.2630498).

716 ⁴³R. Diamant, H.-P. Tan, and L. Lampe, “LOS and NLOS classification for underwater acoustic
717 localization,” *IEEE Trans. Mobile Comput.* **13**(2), 311–323 (2014).

718 ⁴⁴Q. Wang, L. Wei, and R. Kennedy, “Iterative Viterbi decoding, trellis shaping, and multilevel
719 structure for high-rate parity-concatenated TCM,” *IEEE Trans. Commun.* **50**(1), 48–55 (2002)
720 doi: [10.1109/26.975743](https://doi.org/10.1109/26.975743).

721 ⁴⁵L. Marchetti and R. Reggiannini, “An efficient receiver structure for sweep-spread-carrier un-
722 derwater acoustic links,” *IEEE J. Ocean. Eng.* **41**(2), 440–449 (2016).

723 ⁴⁶C. Boya, M. Ruiz-Llata, J. Posada, A. Garcia-Souto, and A. José, “Identification of multiple
724 partial discharge sources using acoustic emission technique and blind source separation,” *IEEE*
725 *Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.* **22**(3), 1663–1673 (2015).

726 ⁴⁷S. Byun, S. Kim, C. Park, K. Kim, and C. Lee, “Cyclostationary analysis of underwater noise
727 for vehicle propeller monitoring,” in *Proc. MTS/IEEE OCEANS*, Monterey, CA (2016).

728 ⁴⁸D. Divins and D. Metzger, “US coastal relief model,” (2016), [http://www.ngdc.noaa.](http://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/coastal/coastal.html)
729 [gov/mgg/coastal/coastal.html](http://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/coastal/coastal.html).

730 ⁴⁹R. Diamant, A. Knap, S. Dahan, I. Mardix, J. Walpert, and S. DiMarco, “THEMO: the Texas
731 A&M – University of Haifa – Eastern Mediterranean Observatory,” in *Proc. MTS/IEEE OCEANS*,
732 Kobe, Japan (2018), to appear.

733 ⁵⁰T. Alexandri and R. Diamant, “A reverse bearings only target motion analysis for autonomous
734 underwater vehicle navigation,” *IEEE Trans. Mobile Comput.* **18**(3), 494–506 (2019) doi: [10.](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMC.2018.2840997)
735 [1109/TMC.2018.2840997](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMC.2018.2840997).

736 ⁵¹“Low-frequency pingers a quick and easy way to relocate an underwater site,”
737 <http://www.jwfishers.com/products/pingers-low.html> (2019).

738 ⁵²V. Chandrasekhar, W. K. Seah, Y. S. Choo, and H. V. Ee, “Localization in underwater sensor
739 networks: survey and challenges,” in *Proc. ACM WUWNet*, Los Angeles, USA (2006).

740 ⁵³N. Al Khanbashi, N. Alsindi, S. Al-Araji, N. Ali, and J. Aweya, “Performance evaluation of CIR
741 based location fingerprinting,” in *Proc. IEEE PIMRC*, Sydney, Australia (2012).

742 **REFERENCES**

743 ¹Note that this information is part of Bellhop's standard output data, and that we do not need to
744 track any propagation history analysis for any of the components of the measured CIR.